

Stability of Nonlinear Thermoelastic Waves in Spinning Anisotropic Membrane Disks

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ABSTRACT

General equations of motion and compatibility governing nonlinear transverse vibrations and waves in membrane-like anisotropic spinning disks are derived, assuming the presence of a temperature field. An harmonic-type nonlinear waves representing the gravest mode in the linear case is then studied. A general wave frequency-wave amplitude relation is discussed for a disk with constant edge temperature and faces freely transferring heat into the surroundings. By means of small temporal disturbance of transverse motion, leading to a system of two coupled differential equations related to the Mathieu-type equation, a detailed analysis of wave stability is given. A numerical example is illustrated by graphs depicting the relation between the wave and spin frequency.

INTRODUCTION

Disks rotating at high speed are employed in many engineering structures, starting from rotors of steam and gas turbines and ending with solar sails, optical and radar reflectors, and precision gyroscopies in spacevehicles. Failures of such disks occurring during the spin have been attributed to flexural vibrations and circumferential waves and then the motions induced by rotation have been examined widely, at first in their linear forms. Historically, the first investigations involved a linear isotropic disk (1-3); they were later extended to include the nonlinear case (4-5). Recently, they were extended to the temperature field and the stability of nonlinear thermoelastic waves in membrane-like spinning disks was investigated (6). With the development of composites, it became worthwhile to reconsider the problem with regard to anisotropic materials, the more so because the anisotropy is a potent instrument in controlling the intensity of motion and stress by appropriate assortment of elastic moduli. A study of this kind was first made in (7) with regard to finite vibrations of a spinning orthotropic membrane. Then this work was extended to circumferential waves and their stability (8). In the present paper, we also intend to extend these works to the problem in stability of nonlinear thermoelastic wave along the study in isotropic material (6).

After deriving the general equations of motion and compatibility governing nonlinear transverse vibrations and waves in membrane-like anisotropic spinning disks, the investigation is confined to harmonic-type nonlinear waves represent-

ing the gravest mode in the linear case. A general wave frequency-wave amplitude relation is discussed for a disk with constant edge temperature and faces freely transferring heat. By means of small temporal disturbances of transverse motion, leading to a system of coupled differential equations, a detailed analysis of wave stability is given. A numerical example is illustrated by graphs.

FUNDAMENTALS

Let us consider a flat circular disk of negligible flexural rigidity and radius a , having a uniform thickness h , and made of a cylindrically orthotropic material. The axis of orthotropy coincide with the axis of symmetry of the disk about which the disk rotates about its central axis with a constant angular velocity Ω . Due to the rotation, transverse vibrations and circumferential waves in the disk are generated, the amplitudes of which are assumed to be comparable with the thickness of the disk and considerably larger than the in-plane displacements. Consequently, the inertia associated with the in-plane motions is disregarded. On the other hand, in view of membrane-like structure of the disk, its motions are controlled by the in-plane tensions, rather than by its stiffness. The disk is assumed in a temperature field which, for the sake of definiteness, is supposed to be stationary and axially symmetric.

We locate the origin of polar coordinates r, θ rotating with the disk, at the center of the middle plane of the disk. With standard notation for stress, the in-plane equations of motion are satisfied by setting

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_r &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \Omega^2 r^2, \\ \sigma_\theta &= \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \Omega^2 r^2, \\ \tau_{r\theta} &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} \right),\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where $\phi = \phi(r, \theta; t)$ is the stress function (in general depending on the time t), while ρ denotes the mass density of the material of the disk. The first governing equation of the problem is the equation of transverse motions (4),

$$\begin{aligned}\left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \dot{w}}{\partial r^2} + \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} - \\ - 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} \right) \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \rho \Omega^2 r^2 \nabla^2 w - \rho \Omega^2 r \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} - \rho \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = 0\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

where $\dot{w} = w(r, \theta; t)$ denotes the transverse deflection of disk and ∇^2 the planar Laplacian operator. In order to establish the second governing equation, one must invoke the compatibility equation (4)

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 e_{rr}}{\partial \theta^2} \overset{\text{lin}}{=} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} (e_{r\theta} \overset{\text{lin}}{=}) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial e_{\theta\theta}}{\partial r} \overset{\text{lin}}{=} \right) \\ - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (e_{rr} \overset{\text{lin}}{=}) = 0,\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

where $e_{ij} \overset{\text{lin}}{=} = e_{ij} - \bar{e}_{ij}$ in which e_{ij} denote the left-hand members of the equations

$$\begin{aligned}e_r &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^2, \\ e_\theta &= \frac{u}{r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{2r^2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} \right)^2, \\ \gamma_{r\theta} &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial r} - \frac{v}{r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta}\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

and the barred symbols stand for the nonlinear terms appearing on the right-hand sides of these equations. Referring to the plane stress constitutive equations of orthotropic thermoelasticity (9), eqs. (8.33c)

$$\begin{aligned} e_r &= \frac{1}{E_r} \sigma_r - \frac{\nu_\theta}{E_\theta} \sigma_\theta + \alpha_r \bar{\Theta} \\ e_\theta &= \frac{1}{E_\theta} \sigma_\theta - \frac{\nu_r}{E_r} \sigma_r + \alpha_\theta \bar{\Theta} \\ \gamma_{r\theta} &= \frac{1}{G_{r\theta}} \tau_{r\theta} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $E_r \nu_\theta = E_\theta \nu_r$ and E_r and E_θ denote the Young's moduli in the radial and hoop directions, respectively; $G_{r\theta}$ is the shear modulus; clearly, ν_θ is the Poisson's ratio associated with the radial tension; α_r and α_θ are the coefficient of thermal expansion in the radial and hoop directions; $\bar{\Theta}$ is the increase of temperature over the ambient temperature. Substitution of eqs. (1), (4) and (5) into eq. (3) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial r^4} + \frac{p^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial r^2 \partial \theta^2} + \frac{k^2}{r^4} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial \theta^4} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial^3 \phi}{\partial r^3} - \frac{p^2}{r^3} \frac{\partial^3 \phi}{\partial r \partial \theta^2} \\ & - \frac{k^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{p^2 + 2k^2}{r^4} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial \theta^4} + \frac{k^2}{r^3} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} \\ & = E_\theta \left[-\frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r \partial \theta} \right)^2 - \frac{2}{r^3} \frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r \partial \theta} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{r^4} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 \right] - s \rho \Omega^2 - E_\theta \left[\alpha_\theta \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\Theta}}{\partial r^2} + (2\alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \bar{\Theta}}{\partial r} \right. \\ & \left. + \alpha_r \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\Theta}}{\partial \theta^2} \right] \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here $w = w(r, \theta, t)$ is the transverse deflection of the membrane, $k^2 = E_\theta/E_r$, $p^2 = \frac{E_\theta}{G_{r\theta}} - 2\nu_\theta$, $s = k^2 + 2\nu_\theta - 3$.

This completes the formulation of the problem which is now reduced to an integration of the system of the heavily nonlinear coupled equations, together with the appropriate boundary conditions.

We assume that the edge of the disk is free from external tractions, so that the mechanical boundary conditions become

$$\sigma_r(a, \theta; t) = 0, \quad \tau_{r\theta}(a, \theta; t) = 0, \quad \text{for all } \theta \text{ and all } t \tag{7}$$

In what follows, we examine harmonic modes of vibration and wave propagation of the form

$$w = A \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^n \cos n\theta \cdot \tau(t), \tag{8}$$

and

$$w = A \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^n \cos n(\theta \pm ct), \tag{9}$$

respectively, with n an integer, A the amplitude, $c = n\omega$, and ω the frequency of motions. Clearly, the assumption above involves a mode with no nodal circles and n nodal diameters as well as the existence of waves travelling both forward (minus sign) and backward (plus sign) in the circumferential direction. This mode is of special interest, inasmuch as in the linear case the mode correspond-

ing to two nodal diameters and no nodal circles was found to be the gravest mode of free vibration (1). As already noted, in practice, the forward wave is found to be much weaker than the backward one, the excitation and sustenance of the latter being attribute to the presence of the atmosphere. We now insert, consecutively, expression (8) and (9) into the governing equation (6) and bearing in mind the boundary conditions (7), arrive at the equations for the function $\tau(t)$ and the stress function in the vibration alternative,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi = & \frac{n(n-1)E\theta A^2}{4\{(2n-1)^2-k^2\}} \left[\left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{2n} - \frac{2n}{(1+k)} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{1+k} \right] \tau^2(t) \\ & - \frac{s\rho\Omega^2 a^4}{8(9-k^2)} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^4 + \frac{(3+\nu\theta)\rho\Omega^2 a^4}{(1+k)(9-k^2)} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{1+k} \\ & - E\theta \left[\alpha_\theta \left\{ \frac{1}{r^k} \int r^k \mathbb{H} dr dr + (k-2) \int \frac{1}{r^k} \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{1}{r^{k-1}} \frac{d\mathbb{H}}{dr} dr dr dr dr \right) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + (2\alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) \left\{ \frac{1}{r^k} \int r^k \int \frac{\mathbb{H}}{r} dr dr dr + (k-1) \int \frac{1}{r^k} \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{\mathbb{H}}{r^k} dr dr dr dr \right) \right\} \right] \\ & + \frac{E\theta}{(1+k)a^{2k}} r^{1+k} \left[\alpha_\theta \left\{ \int r^k \mathbb{H} dr \Big|_{r=a} + (k-2) \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{1}{r^{k-1}} \frac{d\mathbb{H}}{dr} dr dr dr \Big|_{r=a} \right) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + (2\alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) \left\{ \int r^k \int \frac{\mathbb{H}}{r} dr dr \Big|_{r=a} + (k-1) \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{\mathbb{H}}{r^k} dr dr dr \Big|_{r=a} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\tau}{dt^2} + n\omega^2 \left\{ 1 + \frac{(n-1)}{9-k^2} \left[\frac{2(n+1)}{2n+k-1} (3+\nu\theta)(k-1)-s \right] \right\} \tau \\ + \frac{E\theta A^2}{\rho a^4} \frac{n^4(n^2-1)(n-1)(2n-k-1)}{[(2n-1)^2-k^2](2n+k-1)(2n-1)} \tau^3 = 0 \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

The wave solution follows from the equations above by positing $\tau = 1$ and discarding (11). The latter equation coincides with equation (12) in (7) in the case of isothermal condition. The equation was examined in detail in (7) and its discussion will not be pursued further here. Thus, we shall concentrate our attention on the problem of wave propagation.

Turning now to the second governing equation, (2), so far left aside, we substitute (9) and (10), with τ set equal to one, into (2) and arrive at the equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \pm\rho(nc^2 \mp \Omega^2) + \frac{n^2(n-1)^2 E\theta A^2}{2\{(2n-1)^2-k^2\}a^4} \left[(k-1) \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{k-3} - 2(n-1) \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{2(n-2)} \right] \\ - \rho \frac{\Omega^2(n-1)}{9-k^2} \left[(k-1)(3+\nu\theta) \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{k-3} - (k^2+2\nu\theta-3) \right] - T(r) \} x \cos n(\theta \pm ct) = 0 \quad (12) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} T(r) = & (n-1)E\theta \frac{(1+k)}{r^{k+3}} \left[\alpha_\theta \left\{ \int r^k \mathbb{H} dr + (k-2) \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{1}{r^{k-1}} \frac{d\mathbb{H}}{dr} dr dr dr \right) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + (2\alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) \left\{ \int r^k \int \frac{\mathbb{H}}{r} dr dr + (k-1) \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{\mathbb{H}}{r^k} dr dr dr \right) \right\} \right] \\ & - (n-1)E\theta \frac{1}{r^2} \left[\alpha_\theta \left(\mathbb{H} + (k-2) \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{1}{r^{k-1}} \frac{d\mathbb{H}}{dr} dr dr \right) \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + (2\alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) \left\{ \int \frac{\Theta}{r} dr + (k-1) \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{\Theta}{r^k} dr dr \right) \right\} \\
& - (n-1) E_\theta \frac{1-k}{a^{k+3}} \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{k-3} \left[\alpha_\theta \left\{ \int r^k \Theta dr \Big|_{r=a} + (k-2) \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{1}{r^{k-1}} \frac{d\Theta}{dr} dr dr dr \Big|_{r=a} \right) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + (2\alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) \left\{ \int r^k \left(\frac{\Theta}{r} dr dr \Big|_{r=a} + (k-1) \int r^k \int r^{k-2} \left(\frac{\Theta}{r^k} dr dr dr \Big|_{r=a} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (13)
\end{aligned}$$

Since the function $T(r)$ is assigned in advance, equation (12) cannot in general be satisfied for all r in the interval $[0, a]$, and so must be replaced by an approximate equation free of the variable r .

Along the course of study (6), we assume for definiteness that the edge of the disk is kept at the constant temperature Θ_a , while free heat transfer takes place across the faces of the disk into the surroundings at the temperature zero. Such a model crudely approximates the conditions prevailing during the working of a turbine.

In the case of the assumption just made, the equation of uncoupled heat condition takes the form from (9), (10),

$$\nabla^2 \Theta - m^2 \Theta = 0 \quad (14)$$

where $m^2 = 2H/Kh$, H being the surface conductivity and K the thermal conductivity of the material of the disk.

DISK AT A CONSTANT EDGE TEMPERATURE

In this case, the temperature field becomes

$$\Theta(r) = \Theta_a \frac{I_0(mr)}{I_0(ma)} \quad (15)$$

where $I_n(r)$ is the modified Bessel function of the first kind and n -th order.

The stress components are now found to be given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_r = & C_1 \frac{2n}{a^2} \left[\left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{2(n-1)} - \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{k-1} \right] + \frac{\rho \Omega^2 (3+\nu_\theta) a^2}{9-k^2} \left[\left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{k-1} - \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^2 \right] \\
& + E_\theta \Theta'_a \left[- \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_\theta \ell + \alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) m^2 \ell a^{2\ell}}{\{(2\ell+1)^2 - k^2\} 2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell+1)} \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{2\ell} \right. \\
& + \frac{1}{a} \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{k-1} \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_\theta \ell + \alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) m^2 \ell a^{2\ell+1}}{\{(2\ell+1)^2 - k^2\} 2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell+1)} + \\
& \left. + \frac{\alpha_\theta}{(1+k)} \left\{ \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{k-1} - 1 \right\} \right] \quad (16a)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_\theta = & C_1 \frac{2n}{a^2} \left[(2n-1) \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{2(n-1)} - k \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{k-1} \right] \\
& + \frac{\rho \Omega^2 k a^2}{9-k^2} \left[(3+\nu_\theta) \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{k-1} - k (1+3\nu_r) \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^2 \right] \\
& + E_\theta \Theta'_a \left[- \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_\theta \ell + \alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) (2\ell+1) m^2 \ell a^{2\ell}}{\{(2\ell+1)^2 - k^2\} 2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell+1)} \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{2\ell} \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$+ \frac{k}{a} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{k-1} \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_{\theta}\ell + \alpha_{\theta} - \alpha_r)m^2 \ell a^{2\ell+1}}{\{(2\ell+1)^2 - k^2\} 2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell+1)} + \frac{\alpha_{\theta}}{1+k} \left\{ k \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{k-1} - 1 \right\} \quad (16b)$$

$$\tau_{r\theta} = 0 \quad (16c)$$

where

$$C_1 = \frac{E_{\theta} n(n-1)A^2}{4[(2n-1)^2 - k^2]} \text{ and } \Theta_a' = \frac{\Theta_a}{I_0(ma)}$$

In the case of isothermal conditions, equations (16a) and (16b) becomes identical with equations (16) in (8).

Returning now to the examination of (12), in the present case the equation (13) takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} T(r) = & - (n-1)E_{\theta} \Theta_a' \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_{\theta}\ell + \alpha_{\theta} - \alpha_r)m^2 \ell a^{2\ell-2}}{(-k+2\ell+1)(k+2\ell+1)2^{2\ell-1} \ell! \Gamma(\ell)} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{2\ell-2} \\ & - (n-1)(1-k)E_{\theta} \Theta_a' \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{k-3} \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_{\theta}\ell + \alpha_{\theta} - \alpha_r)m^2 \ell a^{2\ell-2}}{(-k+2\ell+1)(k+2\ell+1)2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell+1)} \\ & - \frac{(n-1)(1-k)E_{\theta} \Theta_a' \alpha_{\theta}}{(1+k)a^2} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^{k-3} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

In order to make the equation (12) with (17) instrumental, we apply the orthogonalization procedure of Galerkin. A simple calculation then yields

$$\left(\frac{c}{\Omega}\right)^2 = \alpha \left(\frac{A}{h}\right)^2 + \beta \quad (18)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2\{(2n-1)^2 - k^2\}} \left\{ \frac{2(n-1)}{2n-3} - \frac{k-1}{k-2} \right\} \frac{E_{\theta} h^2}{\rho \Omega^2 a^4} \quad (19a)$$

$$\beta = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \quad (19b)$$

$$\beta_1 = \frac{1}{n(9-k^2)} \left\{ 2(3+\nu_{\theta}) - ns + (n-1) \frac{(k-1)(3+\nu_{\theta})}{k-2} \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_2 = & - \frac{(n-1)}{n} \frac{E_{\theta} \Theta_a'}{\rho \Omega^2 a^2} \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_{\theta}\ell + \alpha_{\theta} - \alpha_r)m^2 \ell a^{2\ell}}{(-k+2\ell+1)(k+2\ell+1)(2\ell-1)2^{2\ell-1} \ell! \Gamma(\ell)} \\ & - \frac{(n-1)(1-k)}{n(k-2)} \frac{E_{\theta} \Theta_a'}{\rho \Omega^2 a^2} \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_{\theta}\ell + \alpha_{\theta} - \alpha_r)m^2 \ell a^{2\ell}}{(-k+2\ell+1)(k+2\ell+1)2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell+1)} \\ & - \frac{(n-1)(1-k)}{n(1+k)(k-2)} \frac{E_{\theta} \Theta_a' \alpha_{\theta}}{\rho \Omega^2 a^2} \end{aligned}$$

and h is the thickness of the membrane. We note that in the isothermal case equation (18) reduces to equation (23) derived in (8). It seems natural to assume β to be always nonnegative in order for the wave velocity to remain real for $A/h \rightarrow 0$.

We note the singular behavior of stresses or wave velocity in the following cases.

(i) Wave propagation becomes linear for

$$n = 1 \quad (20a)$$

Thus, being interested in a nonlinear phenomenon, we have to set $n \geq 2$.

(ii) Stresses become unbounded at the center of the disk for

$$k < 1 \quad (20b)$$

(iii) Stresses and wave velocity become unbounded for

$$k = 3 \text{ or } k = 2n-1 \text{ or } k = 2\ell+1 \quad (20c)$$

(iv) Wave velocity becomes unbounded for

$$k = 2 \quad (20d)$$

In order to avoid too many technicalities. We confine our attention to the case $n = 2$, that is, to the existence of two nodal diameters; this mode seems to be of special importance because, as already mentioned in the linear alternative and for no nodal circles, $n = 2$ corresponds to the gravest mode of free vibrations (1). Furthermore, bearing in mind our conclusions (i) through (iv) above, we exclude from considerations the values which were mentioned on the above.

Let us consider a disk of radius $a = 1\text{m}$, its thickness $h = 0.005\text{m}$ and the mass density $\rho = 7.9 \times 10^3 \text{Ns}^2/\text{m}^4$, made of three types of materials of rather differing elastic properties (Table 1). Let $H = 80 \text{Btu/hr}\cdot\text{ft}^2\text{F}$ ($454.29 \text{W/m}^2\text{C}$), $K = 15 \text{Btu/hr ft F}$ (25.96W/mC), and $\theta_a = 150^\circ\text{C}$. Consequently, $m = 83.67/\text{m}$. Let $A/a = 0.005$, so that the relationship between wave speed ω and a rotation speed Ω are represented by graphs in Figure 1. It is seen that, in the presence of the given temperature field, there is the reduction of ω due to heating. Figure 2 shows the equation (18) for three types of anisotropy defined in Table 1, assuming $\Omega = 10$ rotations per second ($20\pi/\text{s}$).

STABILITY OF TRANSVERSE WAVES

Following the procedure suggested by Bulkeley in (5), we impart a small disturbance $\delta(t)$ to the transverse displacement (9) of the disk, with the temperature field remaining unchanged. Equation (9) is now given the form

$$w = A \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^n \{ \cos n\theta (\cos nct + \delta_1(t)) + \sin n\theta (\mp \sin nct + \delta_2(t)) \} \quad (21)$$

Following a line of argument very similar to that used in the derivation of equation (10) and (12), we substitute (21) into equation (6) and find the perturbed stress function for a disk with its edge free of tractions that $\tau^2(t)$ in equation (10) is replaced by $\{(\cos nct + \delta_1(t))^2 + (\mp \sin nct + \delta_2(t))^2\}$.

It now remains to insert (21) and the perturbed stress function ϕ into the remaining governing equation (2) and apply the orthogonalization procedure. Consequently, disregarding powers of δ_1 and δ_2 higher than the first one, we finally arrive at the equations,

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\delta}_1(t) + \{\lambda + \gamma(1 + \cos 2\tau)\} \delta_1(t) &= \pm \gamma \sin 2\tau \delta_2(t) + (1 - \lambda) \cos \tau \\ \ddot{\delta}_2(t) + \{\lambda + \gamma(1 - \cos 2\tau)\} \delta_2(t) &= \pm \gamma \sin 2\tau \delta_1(t) \mp (1 - \lambda) \sin \tau \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where

$$\gamma = \frac{n(n+1)(n-1)^2 E_0 A}{2\{(2n-1)^2 - k^2\} \rho a^4} \left(\frac{2}{3} - \frac{k-1}{n+k-2} \right) \frac{1}{C^2} \quad (23a)$$

$$\lambda = \lambda_I + \lambda_T \quad (23b)$$

$$\lambda_I = \gamma - \frac{(n-1)s\Omega^2}{n(9-k^2)c^2} + \frac{\Omega^2}{nc^2} + \frac{(k-1)(n+1)(n-1)(3+\nu_\theta)\Omega^2}{n(n+k-2)(9-k^2)c^2}$$

$$\lambda_T = -\frac{(n+1)(n-1)}{n\rho c^2} E_\theta \Theta_a' \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_\theta \ell + \alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) m^2 l_a^2 \ell^{-2}}{(n+2\ell-1)(-k+2\ell+1)(k+2\ell+1)2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell)}$$

$$+ \frac{(k-1)(n+1)(n-1)}{n(n+k-2)\rho c^2} E_\theta \Theta_a' \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2\alpha_\theta \ell + \alpha_\theta - \alpha_r) m^2 l_a^2 \ell^{-2}}{(-k+2\ell+1)(k+2\ell+1)2^{2\ell} \ell! \Gamma(\ell+1)}$$

$$+ \frac{(k-1)(n+1)(n-1)E_\theta \Theta_a' \alpha_\theta}{n(k+1)(n+k-2)\rho a^2 c^2}$$

$$\tau = 2ct$$

and denoted the differentiation with respect to the variable τ by a dot.

The left-hand members of the equations (22) are evidently of the Mathieu type; the equations themselves, although linear, have two unwelcome features, variable coefficients and coupling. A general analysis of the system (22), therefore, becomes exceedingly complicated. But examination of the solution for particular combinations of the parameters γ , λ_I and λ_T is followed by (6).

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Table 1. Three types of anisotropy

	E_r 10^{10}N/m^2	E_θ 10^{10}N/m^2	ν_r	ν_θ	$G_{r\theta}$ 10^{10}N/m^2	k^2	α_r 10^{-6}m/mC	α_θ 10^{-6}m/mC
Isotropy	20.0	20	0.2	0.2	8.3	1	8.5	8.5
Orthotropy I	20.0	2.5	0.24	0.03	4.0	0.125	8.5	4.25
Orthotropy II	2.5	20	0.03	0.24	4.0	8	8.5	17.0

Fig.1 Wave vs. spin frequency

Fig.2 Frequency-amplitude relation